

ECOLOGY AND HUMAN HEALTH IN THE PERIOD OF INDUSTRY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *This article is dedicated to looking at ecology and discussing the situation in today's industrial development. This includes the study and analysis of world affairs, including not only environmental problems, but also the expression of various opinions about human health.*

Keywords: *industry, ecology, nature and man, industrial society, anthropogenic influences, post-industrial era.*

INTRODUCTION.

Nature is a unique complex system, and man and society are its derivatives. It exists and develops at the expense of nature. Man satisfies his needs at the expense of nature. It receives air, water, food, mineral and fuel raw materials from nature and exerts its influence on nature during its life activity. As a result, new objects alien to nature are created. These are: cities and villages, plants and factories, roads, mines, reservoirs, agricultural land, etc. Such anthropogenic landscapes, created by human intelligence and work, will not fail to show their influence on the surrounding natural environment. The rapid growth of the population on earth, the rapid development of science and technology, the uneven distribution of natural resources on the territory of the countries require the maximum possible use of the existing natural resources and, in this way, the acceleration of the development of society. As a result, the laws of interaction between nature and man are violated. Violation of these laws will sooner or later lead to an ecological crisis.

Nowadays, the environmental situation around the world worries many people alike. Ecological destruction is taking a terrible shape before our eyes. There are cases where the issues of environmental protection and efficient use of available natural resources remain relevant.

It has become known that the cause of the current ecological crisis and the one who can get rid of it with his intelligence are humans. Protection of the environment from pollution, economical use of natural resources largely depends on the level of environmental literacy and ecological culture of people, regardless of the society in which they live. To solve environmental problems in our independent republic, increasing the environmental literacy of the population is one of the most important tasks in this regard.

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASIS.

The importance of nature for man and society is huge and diverse. Depending on the aspects of satisfying human needs, it can be distinguished in terms of economic, scientific, health, educational and aesthetic importance.

It can be seen that a person is inextricably linked with the natural environment, both physically and mentally. As a living organism, it is obliged to constantly exchange matter, energy and information with nature in order to ensure its existence. This word means that a person can exist in nature together with it as a component.

It became known that man, as a component of nature, lives together with it. In the process of using nature for his own interests, man exerts various influences on it. For example, in order to obtain food and raw materials, he grows the crops he wants in many areas, plows and irrigates the land, or opens mines to establish various industrial production enterprises. It is difficult to enumerate the types of such production activities of a person.

Human impacts on nature as a result of various production activities are called anthropogenic impacts. Human production takes place in society. Based on this, anthropogenic impact on nature can be understood as the impact of society on nature. Depending on the nature and extent of the interaction of society with nature, various authors suggest to study it in several stages. For example, some authors divide it into four stages: appropriation, agrarian, industrial, and noosphere, while others indicate three stages: biogenic, agrarian, and technogenic. Regardless of how many these stages are and what they are called, one commonality can be noticed in them, which is the increase of society's influence on nature from a simpler and weaker level to a more complex and stronger one. The main reason for this is the gradual improvement of labor tools and production technologies in connection with the development of human consciousness. It should not be forgotten here that as the influence of society on nature increases, the negative influence of nature on society also increases, that is, these effects are reciprocal effects, which are the level of development of the productive forces of society and determined by the nature of production relations. The high quality of the environment is one of the indispensable conditions promoted by the industrial society, and it is the most important indicator of quality changes in the economic and social spheres of society. Even in the largest cities of the world, changes in the structure of the economy, industry, population employment cause not only changes in the anthropogenic impact, but also differences in the state of the environment between cities.

Today, the environmental situation has changed due to changes in the network and territorial structure of industry, the role of road transport and utility resources. The location and power of the sources of anthropogenic influence are the basis for changing the territorial structure of pollution, and a comprehensive analysis of their changes allows to identify the points of greatest environmental stress for the development of urban regulation measures.

In today's era, when the industry is increasing its level of development, the basis for research in this field will be the theoretical foundations of the formation and development of the post-industrial society. In this regard, the views of scientists such as K.E. Aksenova, A.G. Animitsy, V.L. Glazycheva, N.V. Zubarevich, G.M. Lappo, A.G. Makhrova, Yu.G. Saushkina, N.A. Sluki, A.I. Treivish, E.N. Persik, who presented the theoretical and methodological developments of modern geography in the field of urban planning, including, research works of scientists who studied ecological aspects of post-industrial society - D.Bella, V.L.Inozemtsev, M.Castells, A.P.Gorkin; V.R.Bityukova, V.G.Glushkova, I.V.Ivashkina, N.S.Kasimova, M.P.Ratanova conducted large-scale studies of urban areas and analyzed the quality of the urban environment. Chernysheva's researches should be highlighted.

Today, in the rapidly developing post-industrial era, the general laws and features of its changes are being revealed in many large cities of the world. Methods for evaluating the ecological intensity and ecological efficiency of use are being developed, and the main features of the dynamics and territorial structure of the impact level of automobile and air transport are being clarified.

DISCUSSION AND RESULT.

The post-industrial era is the period of the formation and development of the post-industrial society, which in the works of most researchers is the change of social processes under the influence of the development of new technologies, the emergence of a virtual society, that is, from the point of view of space and globalization processes. described. The term "post-industrial society" was introduced for the first time by A. Kumaraswamy at the beginning of the 20th century, who spoke not about the formation of a fundamentally new society, but about the replacement of the industrial period of society's development with a larger society. A. Pentti followed the same position. In 1958, the American sociologist D. Riesman used the term "post-industrial society" to define the "leisure society" in the title of his article.

The post-industrial economy is an integral part of the post-industrial society, based on the service and high-tech economy, which produces high-quality competitive products for the world market. In the raw materials, agricultural and industrial sectors of the world economy, competition between participants is high, which means low profits. In developed countries, industrialization is replaced by post-industrialization. At the same time, in post-industrial countries, agrarian, industrial and post-industrial structures can be observed to coexist simultaneously - in different proportions and spatial forms. In the post-industrial society, the service sector mainly consists of information processing. Modern high-profit industries: pharmaceuticals, specialized electronics, telecommunications, computer equipment, mining industry using the latest technologies, petrochemicals are expanding even in times of economic stagnation. This type of economy is typical for the countries of Europe and the USA, which have long transferred their production capacities to the countries of Asia and Latin America.

The industrial sector of the economy is moving from developed countries to developing countries, and within the country from large cities to smaller cities and suburbs, and the direction of this industrial area depends on the city government. Globally, there is a polarization of countries similar to the division of post-industrial societies into the intellectual class and the rest of society. The situation is the same in cities. First of all, this is reflected in the increase in the demands of the creative class for the quality of the urban environment: beautified parks, pedestrian streets, creative clusters appear - this helps to increase the creative potential of the population. On the other hand, there is a territorial segmentation between the areas where creative labor is used. Disadvantaged areas with a minimally developed population and infrastructure and places for cultural recreation do not exist.

CONCLUSION.

So, along with conveniences and advantages, disadvantages can also be observed. There are also negative situations. One of such negative situations is damage to nature and ecology.

The set of negative changes in nature causes great harm to human health. The general level of morbidity of the population is constantly increasing, respiratory, gastrointestinal, oncological, allergic, heart, blood vessel and nervous diseases are increasing, and new unknown diseases are appearing. The AIDS disease, which is shaking the world, is attracting more and more people. As a result of negative changes in nature, environmental problems characterized by the deterioration of the human habitat are also occurring. Depending on the scope of such problems, they can conditionally be divided into global or universal, regional and local ecological problems.

A brief analysis of the influence of man and society on nature and on himself shows that the main factor that destroys nature is that people treat nature incorrectly, irrationally, and

uneducated in the process of meeting their needs. The main way to prevent negative human impact on nature is to understand the laws of nature and society and use them wisely for human benefits. It is important for a person to properly master nature and maintain the relationship between nature and society at the optimal level. For this, it is necessary for a person to have a sufficiently formed system of certain ecological knowledge. Therefore, it can be concluded that it is one of the most urgent issues of the present time that every person of the society, regardless of who he is, what kind of task he performs, is one of the most urgent issues, in relation to the above opinions, theoretical and practical processes.

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